

MANUFACTURING METHOD OF A THERMOPLASTIC SEMI-FINISHED PRODUCT AS REINFORCEMENT IN LAMINATE THICKNESS DIRECTION

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Keywords: Delamination, Thermoplastic CFRP, Z-pins

ABSTRACT

This work presents carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic pins as thickness reinforcements for carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates. The pins have a staple-like geometry (so called clips) and are intruded into dry fabrics during preforming. In order to ease the pin handling, the processing and to stabilize the pin during the intrusion, several pins are fixed to a thermoplastic tape. The pins and the carrier tape define a semi-finished product. The base material for the pins is a rod-shaped consolidated composite made of carbon fiber reinforced PA 6. A thermoforming process is presented, which forms the base material into the staple-like geometry and simultaneously bonds the pin onto the carrier tape. The influence of different CFRP pin widths at a constant volume content on interlaminar properties was investigated in G_{IC} tests. The smallest investigated pin width of 1 mm increased the interlaminar toughness compared to unreinforced samples by 113%.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates often consist of multiple layers of carbon fiber textiles. CFRP laminates are predominately configured in order to bear loads in fiber direction by a large percentage of in-plane continuous fibers [1, 2]. The anisotropic properties of composite materials are an advantage for lightweight design, but show disadvantages considering shear, impact and out of plane forces, respectively. These loads generally lead to interlaminar failure (delamination) of the composite, which is mainly dependent on the mechanical response of the matrix (polymer) or the fiber matrix interface. There are several ways in order to increase this interlaminar fracture toughness. One way describes the chemical modification of matrix material (e.g. toughening) while another way is to introduce reinforcing fibers (high stiffness, high strength) in composite laminate thickness direction. These reinforcements shall bridge delaminations and thereby suppress their propagation.

2 STATE OF THE ART/INVESTIGATIONS

Through-thickness reinforcing methods like tufting and z-pinning are well known from the aeronautical and automobile sector, particularly in the region of bonded joints [3]. The state of the art of reinforcing processes is mainly divided in either dry/cured reinforcing fibers or dry/preimpregnated basic materials.

Tufting is a one-sided stitching process having its origin in the carpet industry and is used in the CFRP sector as well [4]. The process is defined by reinforcing a dry fabric stack, consisting of multiply layers, by a dry glass/carbon fiber. This fiber is inserted automatically in fabric thickness direction (z direction) by a threaded needle, which penetrates the dry fabric stack completely. The needle sets back on the same path, while the fiber remains in the stack and forms typical loops on the back side. The z-fiber remains inside the fiber stack because of the frictional forces between the reinforcing fiber and the fabric. If the fiber stack is too thin, an additional support bed is necessary in order to produce enough friction for the remaining of the z-fiber. Figure 1a shows the principle of the tufting process.

Figure 1: Principle of the tufting and the z-pinning process [4, 5]

The z-pinning technique is mainly used for prepreg applications like stiffened panels in aircraft skins [1]. The z-reinforcements are pultruded CFRP (thermoset) pins with a defined diameter and length which are carried mostly in a square pattern by a flat, rigid polymer foam creating a semi-finished product (Figure 1b). The foam guarantees the spacing and lateral support during insertion. The pin foam is positioned on a prepreg specimen and the pins are inserted via an ultrasonic pistol (ultrasonically-assisted pinning UAZ[®]) into the prepreg. The ultrasonic stress waves cause moderate heating of the pin that softens the resin matrix and eases the insertion [2]. This manufacturing step is done automatically [5] in order to guarantee an orthogonal pin insertion. After the pin insertion the compressed foam and the remaining pin shafts have to be removed.

A recent investigation was done by Löbel, who inserted metallic staple-like pins in order to enhance interlaminar properties of double-lap joints [6]. There were two insertion methods investigated, which both created a form closure on the rear side of the specimen. One principle described the inserting of staples after curing of the composite (drilling was necessary). The other method described the insertion of staples into dry fiber plies by using a conventional staple gun. Figure 2 shows the principle of the staple and the form closure on the back side.

Figure 2: Schematic principle of staple-like pins [6]

Improvements of interlaminar toughness are an undisputed effect of all presented methods, which is proved by several references [2, 4, 6]. Fibers in thickness (orthogonal) direction implicate improvements of mechanical properties in this direction. Defined comparisons of reinforcing effects considering mechanical properties was already done by [7]. However the methods may also be compared by the amount and the complexity of their processing steps. Restricting points so far, besides e.g. mechanical drawbacks in fiber direction, are the effort that needs to be done to insert reinforcements in the base material or post process after the insertion. In order to reach commercial quantities more work is required to develop automated, low-cost manufacturing methods for inserting z-pins [2]. The pin, as it is presented in [6], intrudes the preform itself, without the usage of a threaded needle or a pin carrying foam, because of its staple-like geometry (in the style of stationery application). However metallic reinforcements have lower specific properties than CFRP components.

This paper presents the manufacturing of staple-like pins (clips) made of CFRP and its application as through-thickness reinforcements for composites materials. One focus of this investigation is to avoid metallic-hybrid composite structures and use CFRP materials, which have larger increased specific properties than metals. The second focus lies in a simple insertion technique, which is made of few manufacturing steps.

3 CFRP CLIP AND INSERTION INTO PREFORM

The pins presented in this paper are made of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics. As pin material carbon fiber reinforced PA 6 from Celstran (CFR-TP PA6 CF60-01) is used. The pin is axially symmetric and has a staple-like shape (clip) with two pins connected by a foot. The pin has a large length to width (thickness) ratio and additionally a chamfered tip for easier insertion into the fabric. The foot has a large width to thickness ratio. Figure 3 shows the dimensions at a schematic and a manufactured clip. The pin has a rectangular cross section due to the used raw material (chapter 4).

Figure 3: Dimensions of a schematic and a manufactured clip with chamfered tips

In order to ease the transport of a large amount of pins and enable the insertion of several pins at a time, the clips are bonded to a carrier foil. A semi-finished product is created. The flat foot, with its relative large surface, is connected to the carrier foil by fusion bonding. In order to realize proper bonding the clip matrix and the foil consist of the same polymer. In this case the carrier is slightly larger than the foot length. Figure 4a shows a clip tape scheme and Figure 4b presents a flexed clip tape with four clips (8 pins) at a distance of 10 mm. The flexibility of the carrier tape is important for the application on e.g. uneven, curved preforms. Table 1 demonstrates the dimensions of the clip shown in the figures before.

Figure 4: Clip tape (scheme) and flexed clip tape

Pin height	5 mm	Pin width	1 mm	Pin thickness	0,5
Pin chamfer	45°	Foot thickness	0,25	Foot width	3,0
Foot length	5 mm	Foil thickness	100 µm		

Table 1: Clip and clip tape dimensions

Several pins are inserted into the preform in order to enhance the interlaminar toughness of the laminate. The pin has a chamfered tip, which eases the mechanical introduction into the dry preform in comparison to a flat pin tip. The pin is loaded by a compression forces and transfers it to the foot. Furthermore, the intersection between pin and foot (clip radius) stabilizes the pin laterally during the insertion by absorbing occurring bending moments if the insertion force is not absolute orthogonal. Either a process like the staple gun mechanism is chosen or, as it is shown in Figure 5, the principle of pushing the preform onto the pins of the clip tape. This method was chosen and used predominantly for the preparation of the specimens for G_{IC} tests, as they are described in chapter 6.

Figure 5: Principle pin insertion into preform

The pin height is slightly smaller than the compacted preform thickness in order not to cause any damage to e.g. the vacuum bag if infiltrated by vacuum assisted process (VAP®).

4 HOT DIE FORMING MANUFACTURING METHOD

As well as metallic staples, CFRP clips need to be formed before insertion into the preform. The manufacturing method is based on a hot die-forming process of consolidated slit composite tapes (raw material). It has the advantages of not requiring any infusion, but needs to be formed above matrix melting temperature.

The raw material is produced by tape lying. The tapes consist of four layers that were processed with 240°C / 4 bar and create a composite thickness of 0,5 mm. It is then slit to a width of 1 mm. Furthermore, the tape needs to be cut to the correct length before forming. Its length calculates from the sum of twice the pin length, foot length and twice the radius circumference (Figure 3a). During the cutting process the chamfer is applied on both ends of the slit tape as well. The cutting is done manually using a standard box cutter.

Figure 6 shows the manufacturing principle. The construction consists of a stamp and a mold which is positioned in a kind of press. The mold is made of two bars with a rectangular cross section, which have milled notches on their top in a distance of 10 mm. Each of the upper notches guides a slit tape (yellow) and constrains its position laterally. Parallel to this movement the carrier tape (in red) is inserted into the mold. A heated stamp is positioned between the bars and moves in vertical direction. In the case of PA 6 the stamp has a temperature of 240°C. The heated stamp forms the slit/chamfered tape into the clip shape. Simultaneously, the stamp presses with 50 bar on the foot in order to create a bonding with the carrier foil and create its flat shape. After the cooling of the stamp to a temperature below the melting temperature of PA 6, the clip tape is removed from the mold. The hot die-forming process has the ability of being scaled up by inserting a larger amount of slit tapes at the same time. Respectively, the dimensions of the stamp and mold would have to be increased, but the process would not be changed in its manufacturing steps.

The microscopic pictures above show in particular the four tape layers and carbon fibers filaments with elliptical shapes. The ellipses are explained by the filament position relative to the polished surface. The larger the main axis of the ellipse, the smaller is the angle between the longitudinal filament axis and the polished plane. Thus Figure 8a shows a nearly parallel distribution of the filaments in the four layers along the pin. Whereas Figure 8b shows the clip radius with a non-homogenous distribution of the filament orientation, comparing inner and outer radius and especially considering the four single layers. The stronger the filaments are disaligned from their former unidirectional orientation, the shorter is the main axis of the ellipse. These lengths are highlighted in red while the minor axes measure always 7 μm and therefore are not highlighted. The filament orientation may be divided in four groups corresponding to the four layers of the composite. Table 2 shows that filaments, which are closer to the inner radius, have an increased deviation from the unidirectional direction than the external filaments. The layer numbering begins at the inner radius.

Layer number	Average main axis length [mm]	Average deviation from unidirectional orientation [°]
1	10,7 ($\pm 1,2$)	41,0
2	16,2 ($\pm 4,0$)	25,6
3	27,5 ($\pm 5,1$)	14,7
4	64,8 ($\pm 47,5$)	6,2

Table 2: Main axis length and deviation from unidirectional orientation

The filament disalignment has its origin in the hot forming process. The filaments leave their original aligned position because of increased temperature (above PA 6 melting temperature) and forces required for the forming of the radius and the flat clip foot. Furthermore, the forming process promotes the forming of resin rich zones, as it is visible on the inner radius. The chamfered tip, which is not deformed in the forming process shows four layers as well but no resin rich zones within the layers.

6 INTERLAMINAR TESTS

In order to investigate the reinforcing effect of the clips, unreinforced and reinforced specimens were tested in G_{IC} tests (Mode I-Tests). The G_{IC} test is used for investigation of the interlaminar toughness of composite materials. A force perpendicular to the composite's mid-plane is introduced by so called loading blocks and starts a controlled crack along the longitudinal axis of the specimen (Figure 9). The energy per area which is required for the crack propagation is regarded as the G_{IC} value.

Figure 9: G_{IC} test

Specimens with different pin widths were tested in G_{IC} tests. The specimens were reinforced in total by a constant volume content of 0,3% across a reinforcement area of 80 mm x 35 mm. The specimens were configured as follows:

- Specimen 1 (S1) is reinforced with a pin width of 1 mm; in total 9 clips
- Specimen 2 (S2) is reinforced with a pin width of 1,8 mm; in total 5 clips
- Specimen 3 (S3) is reinforced with a pin width of 3 mm; in total 3 clips

The CFRP pins had the dimensions as described in Table 1 with the exception of pin height of 4 mm and the clip foot length of 10 mm, in order to avoid stress concentrations. The specimens were made of 6 layers carbon fiber fabric ($0^\circ/90^\circ$ made of Mitsubishi Grafil 24 k fiber) and were infiltrated using VAP[®] with an epoxy matrix system (CR-80 Sika[®]). The tests based on 250 mm long and 35 mm wide rectangular-shaped specimens. The standard G_{IC} specimen width was changed to the standard width of 25 mm in order to avoid edge effects caused by the reinforcements. On one of its sides the specimen contained a 25 mm long PTFE foil in the center plane in order to initiate a controlled crack. The pins were positioned in the described pattern 35 mm behind the foil. The tests were performed at a Hegewald & Peschke (100 kN) tensile testing machine. The test velocity was 10 mm/min. The pins were inserted in the preforms in the way it is described in chapter 3. Figure 10 shows the general specimen dimensions including the pin position for S1, S2 and S3 with a clip spacing of 10 mm, 20 mm and 40 mm. The rectangular spots represent the pins.

Figure 10: G_{IC} specimen dimensions

The following force-displacement graphs (Figure 11) show an unreinforced (UR) and three reinforced specimens (S1, S2, S3).

Figure 11: Force displacement diagram of G_{IC} tests

All specimens show approximately the same initial force (around 180 N) because pins do not influence the initiation of delaminations [2]. Furthermore, steady increases and abrupt drops in the force are noticeable during the test. This applies to all reinforced specimens as well as the unreinforced. The unsteady behavior of the UR has its origin in the use of a fabric. The crack propagation for a fabric based specimens is not stable, due to its undulations caused by the interwoven fiber architecture. In contrast a unidirectional (UD) prepreg sample has a stable crack propagation, as is described in [8]. Considering the reinforced specimens, there are larger drops of force visible. This is caused by the blocking and release of the crack propagation at the pin position. The pins are bridging the delamination (crack bridging) and are pulled out of the beam arms during the tests, which was described by several references before [2]. The large blocking of crack propagation led to failure of the specimen arms (especially for S1). For this reason the G_{IC} values were calculated with a crack length of 90 mm by means of DIN EN 6033. Six specimens were tested for each configuration.

Figure 12: G_{IC} values of the specimens: UR, S1, S2, S3

Figure 12 shows that S1 has the largest increase (113 %) in the G_{IC} value in respect to the UR test samples. S2 and S3 show smaller enlargements of 66 % and 27 %. The clear difference in strengthening effect between the reinforced samples (S1, S2, S3) occurs because of the difference in contact area between the pins and the laminate. If the pin width decreases, the pin amount increases. This leads to a larger contact area per delamination area and lead thus to larger friction forces during

the pin pull-out. Friction is the dominating mechanism for energy absorption [8]. These results correspond with research of [9], who investigated carbon epoxy z-pins reinforced unidirectional prepreg samples with different diameters at constant volume content.

7 CONCLUSION

A staple-like pin (clip), respectively clip tape, made of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic are presented. A hot die-forming process for the manufacturing of the clips was successfully developed. Thus an alternative for the state of the art reinforcing methods was created with regards to simple intrusion into preforms, non-metallic-hybrid composite and a significant reinforcing effect on interlaminar toughness. The used pin widths are larger than the ones described in z-pinning literature. The reason for this is the manual slitting, which is necessary before pin manufacturing at current prototype level. Next steps are the substitution of the slit composite tape by a thermoplastic pultruded raw material, to enable diameters of less than 1 mm at repeatable quality. With the current form of the clip the reinforcing effect is purely based on friction. Future work will focus on further increasing the effect of the reinforcements by realizing, form closure on the back side of the base material via deformation the pins after insertion.

8 REFERENCES

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